

ZnGa₂O₄ polycrystalline thin-film preparation using hydrothermally synthesized nanoparticles

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Abstract

Polycrystalline ZnGa₂O₄ (ZGO) thin films were fabricated on quartz substrates using hydrothermally synthesized ZGO nanoparticles with Zn and O deficiencies. The ZGO thin films were formed by annealing the nanoparticle-coated substrate in air at the temperature range of 500–800 °C. Although the annealing process increased the crystallite size and weakened the quantum size effects decreasing the energy gap (E_g), the ZGO thin film annealed at 800 °C still showed high E_g value of 4.59 eV. A photocurrent (I_p) was generated in the thin films at an applied voltage of 40 V under irradiation solar-blind (SB) light conditions (with a wavelength of 254 nm), whereas no I_p was induced following exposure

to ultraviolet light at 365 nm; that is, the ZGO thin films showed the capability to distinguish SB light and non-SB light. In addition, the repetition of the photocurrent response to SB light was confirmed for the ZGO thin film annealed at 800 °C, where the photocurrent increased with the applied voltage. The ratio of the I_p to the dark current (I_D , current without irradiation) increased by a factor of 8.8 as the annealing temperature was increased from 500 °C to 800 °C owing to the decrease in I_D . At high-annealing temperatures, the I_D was decreased due to the improved crystallinity resulting from the increase in the number of oxygen vacancies. The present ZGO thin films and control of their I_p characteristics by the annealing temperature during preparation can aid in future durable SB photodetector applications.

Keywords: ZnGa₂O₄, thin film, nanoparticle, hydrothermal synthesis, photocurrent

Relevance summary

In this study, polycrystalline ZGO thin films were fabricated on a quartz substrate using hydrothermally synthesized ZGO nanoparticles with Zn and O deficiencies by annealing at different temperatures in air. In the present ZGO films, the effects of annealing temperature on the structural, optical, and photocurrent properties were elucidated. Further, the annealing temperature improved the photocurrent characteristics of the resulting ZGO thin film, demonstrating its applicability to the detection of SB light.

1. Introduction

Optically transparent and electrically conductive materials have attracted considerable attention because of their widespread use as transparent electrodes in various applications, such as liquid-crystal displays, solar panels, and touch panels [1–3]. Optical transparency and electrical conductivity are incompatible in metal oxides [4], but Sn-doped In_2O_3 [5], Al-doped ZnO [6], F-doped SnO_2 [7], Si-doped Ga_2O_3 [8], MgIn_2O_4 [9], and ZnGa_2O_4 (ZGO) [10, 11] exhibit excellent transparency and conductivity. Among these, Ga_2O_3 and ZGO have the potential to be used in solar-blind (SB) photodetectors because of their wide bandgaps (E_g) in the ranges of 4.9–5.2 eV for Ga_2O_3 [12] and 4.8–5.2 eV for ZGO [13, 14], respectively. SB light is deep-ultraviolet (UV) light with a wavelength in the range of 220–280 nm and is harmful to humans. Sunlight typically contains SB light, which is absorbed by the ozone layer, resulting in its scarcity at the earth's surface. Moreover, SB light is generated by the radiation emitted from flames. Considering the aforementioned features of SB light, an SB photodetector is considered useful in ozone-layer monitoring, flame detection, space-to-space communications, and other applications [15]. Therefore, many studies have been extensively conducted on the SB photodetector using Ga_2O_3 and ZGO, including the highly sensitive and flexible Ga_2O_3 SB photodetectors [16], high-performance metal-oxide-semiconductor field effect transistors based on Ga_2O_3 [17], self-powered ZGO photodetectors [13] and ultrafast responses ZGO photodetectors [18].

ZGO is a particularly attractive metal oxide owing to its spinel-type crystal structure. This is because spinel-type metal oxides have thermal, mechanical, and chemical stabilities, and exhibit different physical properties depending on the combination of tetrahedral site ions and octahedral site ions. ZGO has Zn^{2+} at the tetrahedral site and Ga^{3+} at the octahedral site, and it possesses excellent catalytic and optical properties in addition to electrical properties. Therefore, ZGO can be used to fabricate multifunctional materials that can withstand mechanical shocks and adverse environments. In addition to ZGO-based SB photodetectors, photocatalysts used for pollutant degradation and phosphors for display devices have been produced using ZGO [19, 20]. In recent years, the application of ZGO as a photocatalyst has shown great promise a future solution to pollution and the use of renewable energy.

The electrical conductivity of ZGO is enhanced by increasing the number of oxygen vacancies generated by annealing in a reducing atmosphere [10, 21], because oxygen vacancies play an important role in supplying conduction carriers in ZGO. In a previous study, we hydrothermally synthesized ZGO nanoparticles with a large number of oxygen vacancies from a precursor solution with a reduced pH [22]. These ZGO nanoparticles exhibit strong luminescence from defects, including oxygen vacancies; therefore, they are expected to exhibit high electrical conductivity. However, the photocurrent characteristics of hydrothermally synthesized ZGO nanoparticles have rarely been investigated [23], because their electrical properties cannot be directly measured due to their small size. Therefore, the photocurrent properties of

hydrothermally synthesized ZGO nanoparticles should be investigated for future applications in SB optical devices.

In this study, we fabricated ZGO thin films using ZGO nanoparticles hydrothermally synthesized from a precursor solution with low pH. In order to evaluate the photocurrent properties of the small nanoparticles, they were made into the thin films by a binder-based technique. The structural, optical, and photocurrent characteristics of the ZGO thin films under SB light irradiation were investigated. Additionally, the effect of the annealing temperature during thin-film preparation on these characteristics were examined.

2. Experimental

2.1 Hydrothermal synthesis of ZGO nanoparticles

ZGO nanoparticles were hydrothermally synthesized for the thin-film fabrication. Two solution route methods were used to prepare the precursor solutions [24]. First, two source solutions were prepared separately, namely an aqueous solution of zinc sulfate hydrate (2.5 mmol, $\text{ZnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 99.5 %, Kishida Chemicals) and sodium hydroxide (5.0 mmol, NaOH, 98.0 %, Wako Chemicals) dissolved in 50 mL deionized (DI) water, and a solution of gallium (III) sulfate hydrate [2.5 mmol, $\text{Ga}_2(\text{SO}_4)_3 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$; salt concentration of 53.8%; Mitsuwa Chemical Co., Ltd.] and NaOH (15.0 mmol) dissolved in 50 mL DI water. The aforementioned solutions were stirred separately for 1 h. Subsequently, they were mixed and stirred for 1 h, obtaining the precursor solution with a pH of 5.2. A 25-mL Teflon cylinder was filled with the precursor solution, placed in a stainless-steel pressure vessel, and then sealed. For the hydrothermal reactions, the pressure vessel was heated to 200 °C for 1 h using an oven, maintained for 10 h, and then cooled to room temperature. After the reaction, the precipitated products were extracted by ultrasonication with DI water, followed by centrifugation and decanting. These processes were repeated twice. Finally, the powdered ZGO nanoparticle sample was obtained by vacuum drying the extracted products at 80 °C.

2.2 Preparation of ZGO thin films

The binder was synthesized by dissolving 2.0 g ethyl cellulose and 4.0 g α -terpineol in 20 mL ethanol while stirring at 50 °C for 30 min. Subsequently, the ethanol dispersion of ZGO nanoparticles (0.3 g ZGO nanoparticles and 0.5 mL ethanol) was mixed with binder (1.0 g). The resulting material is referred to as the ZGO nanoparticles mixed with the binder.

ZGO thin films were prepared using ZGO nanoparticles. The surface of the quartz substrate (1.0 cm \times 1.0 cm) was ultrasonically cleaned with acetone and isopropyl alcohol and then treated with air plasma to remove organic contaminants. The ZGO nanoparticles mixed with binder were spin-coated onto the substrate at 5000 rpm for 30 s and baked at 100 °C in air for 10 min. Finally, the substrates were heated to the set temperatures of 500, 600, 700, 800, and 900 °C in air in an electric furnace for 1 h. The substrate was held at the set temperature for 1 h and then cooled naturally to room temperature.

2.3 Characterization of ZGO nanoparticles and thin films

The phases of the obtained ZGO nanoparticles and thin films were characterized by X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis using a SmartLab spectrometer (Rigaku) with Cu K α radiation ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$). The sizes and crystal structures of the nanoparticles were evaluated by transmission electron microscopy (TEM; JEM-2100, JEOL) at an acceleration voltage of 200 kV. The surface morphologies and thicknesses of the thin films were observed using scanning electron microscopy (SEM, JSM-6010PLUS/LA, JEOL).

The optical absorption edges of the nanoparticles and thin films were evaluated by UV-Visible (UV-Vis) diffuse reflectance and transmittance spectroscopy, respectively, using a V570DS spectrometer (JASCO). The atomic states of the films were analyzed by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS, ESCA-3400, Shimadzu) with an Al K α source (1486 eV).

2.4 Evaluation of the photocurrent

Figure 1 shows a schematic of the ZGO thin film with comb-shaped electrodes and the circuit used to evaluate its electrical characteristics under SB-light irradiation. Au thin-film electrodes with a thickness of 200 nm were patterned on the surface of the ZGO thin films by sputtering using a metal mask. The current–voltage (I – V) characteristics were measured by sweeping an applied voltage from -40 V to $+40$ V using a digital electrometer (8252, ADCMT). The measurements were performed with and without UV irradiation in air using a UV lamp at the wavelengths of 254 and 365 nm (SLUV-8, AS ONE). The 254-nm UV light ($1013 \mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2$) was used as the SB light, whereas the 365-nm UV light ($1047 \mu\text{W}/\text{cm}^2$) was used as the non-SB light for comparison. The photocurrent responses were measured using the digital electrometer while the SB light was repeatedly turned on and off for 60 s on the tested ZGO thin films.

Fig. 1 Schematic of the polycrystalline ZnGa_2O_4 (ZGO) thin film with comb electrodes for the photocurrent measurement

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Structural characteristics of the ZGO nanoparticles and thin films

Figure 2a shows a TEM image of the powder sample obtained by hydrothermal synthesis, from which the nanocrystals were identified. Figure 2b shows the selected area electron diffraction (SAED) pattern of the nanoparticles with the bright rings corresponding to the (110), (220), (311), (400), (511), and (440) planes in the cubic spinel structure of ZGO, indicating that the nanoparticles were ZGO. The size distribution of the nanoparticles determined by TEM is shown in Fig. 2c. From the Gaussian fit, the ZGO nanoparticles were uniformly small with an average size of 9.94 ± 2.21 nm.

Fig. 2 (a) Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) image of the hydrothermally synthesized ZGO nanoparticles and (b) corresponding selected area electron diffraction pattern. (c) Particle-size distribution with Gaussian function fit (curve) of the ZGO nanoparticles. The mean values and standard deviations are shown in the plot

Figure 3a shows the cross-sectional SEM image of the ZGO thin film annealed at 500 °C. The films had a thickness of 4.85 μm. Figure 3b–f show the SEM images of the surfaces of the ZGO thin films

annealed at different temperatures. Slight variations were noted in the surface morphology even at different annealing temperatures, and the aggregated nanoparticles ranged in size from submicrons to a few micrometers. The binder was removed by combustion as the annealing was performed in air at a higher temperature than the decomposition temperatures of the binder, which were 110 and 315 °C for α -terpineol and ethyl cellulose, respectively [25].

Fig. 3 (a) Scanning electron microscopy images of the cross-section of the ZGO thin film on the substrate surface annealed at 500 °C. Surface images of the ZGO thin films annealed at (b) 500 °C, (c) 600 °C, (d) 700 °C, (e) 800 °C, and (f) 900 °C

Figure 4a shows the XRD patterns of the obtained nanoparticles and thin films. The major peaks correspond to the standard data for the ZGO spinel phase (PDF-00-038-1240), suggesting the formation of ZGO thin films. The peak intensities were normalized to those of the (311) peak at approximately $2\theta = 36^\circ$. β -Ga₂O₃ was confirmed as an impurity phase for the thin film annealed at 900 °C. Thus, the subsequent measurements and analyses were performed on the single-phase ZGO thin films annealed at 500–800 °C. The comparison of the (440) peaks in Fig. 4b demonstrates the narrowing of the peak width at increasing annealing temperatures. The lattice spaces calculated using the 2θ of the (440) peak are plotted as a function of the annealing temperature in Fig. 4c. The lattice space slightly increased to the standard ZGO value of 1.4734 Å (PDF-00-038-1240) as the annealing temperature increased. The crystallite sizes of the ZGO thin films were calculated using the Scherrer equation [26]

$$D = \frac{k\lambda}{\beta \cos \theta} \quad (1)$$

where D is the crystallite size, k is the so-called Scherrer constant, λ is the X-ray wavelength, β is the full-width-at-half-maximum intensity of the diffraction peak (FWHM), and θ is the diffraction angle. k depends on the crystallite size distribution, indices of the diffraction lines, and the actual definition used for β [27].

The value of k ranges from 0.62 to 2.08; $k = 0.9$ was used in this study. Microstrain in the crystallite also effects β , which must be considered for accurate analysis. Thus, in this study, the calculated values of crystallite size represent estimates [28]. The crystallite sizes calculated using the (440) peak are plotted against the annealing temperatures in Fig. 4d. The crystallite size of the ZGO nanoparticles without annealing was 10.00 Å, as determined from XRD, which was almost consistent with the average particle sizes of 9.94 ± 2.21 nm obtained by TEM. Therefore, the crystallite size of the ZGO thin films increased with the annealing temperature. As the peak width narrowed with the increasing annealing temperatures (Fig. 4b), the lattice space (Fig. 4c) and crystallite size increased (Fig. 4d), thereby improving the crystallinity of the ZGO thin films.

Fig. 4 (a) X-ray diffraction patterns normalized by the intensity of the (311) peaks. (b) Enlarged view of the (440) peaks of the hydrothermally synthesized ZGO nanoparticles and thin films annealed in the range of 500–900 °C. (c) Relationship between the lattice space of the (440) planes and annealing temperatures. The dotted line is the lattice space of the ZGO nanoparticles. (d) Relationship between the crystallite size and annealing temperatures. The dotted line is the crystallite size of the ZGO nanoparticles

3.2 Annealing effects on the atomic states in the ZGO nanoparticles and thin films

XPS measurements were performed on the ZGO nanoparticles and thin films to investigate the effects of annealing temperature on the atomic states. Figure 5 shows the XPS spectra of (a) Zn 2p, (b) Ga 2p, and (c) O 1s for the ZGO samples. The binding energies of Zn 2p_{3/2}, Zn 2p_{1/2}, Ga 2p_{3/2}, Ga 2p_{1/2}, and O 1s were approximately 1022, 1045, 1118, 1145, and 531 eV, respectively, and differed for the samples annealed at different temperatures (Fig. 5a-c), indicating the changes in the cation interstitial point defect states in the ZGO samples with the annealing temperature [29, 30]. The O1s spectra shifted to a higher binding energy with an increase in the annealing temperature, as shown in Fig. 5c. The fitting of the O1s spectra revealed two peaks, as shown in Figs. 5d and 5e. The peak at approximately 530.8 eV originates from oxygen ions at the lattice points of the crystal structure and is denoted as O_I, whereas that at a higher binding energy of ~ 532.1 eV is correlated with the oxygen vacancies and is denoted as O_{II} [29–31]. Therefore, oxygen vacancies were observed in the structure of the ZGO thin films as well as in that of the hydrothermally synthesized nanoparticles [22]. The peaks exhibited different intensities for the thin films annealed at 500 and 800 °C, as shown in Figs. 5d and 5e.

Fig. 5 (a) X-ray photoelectric spectroscopy (XPS) analysis of the ZGO samples: (a) Zn 2p, (b) Ga 2p, and (c) O 1s spectra. O 1s XPS spectrum of the ZGO thin films annealed at (d) 500 °C and (e) 800 °C. (f) Plot of the ratio of the integrated intensities of O_{II} and O_I as a function of the annealing temperature. The dotted line is for the ZGO nanoparticles. (g) Plot of the atomic ratio of Zn to Ga as a function of annealing temperature. The dotted line denotes the ratio value for ZGO nanoparticles

The ratios of the integrated intensities of the O_{II} and O_I peaks (O_{II}/O_I) are plotted as a function of the annealing temperature in Fig. 5f. The number of oxygen vacancies increases as a function of the annealing temperature. However, the crystallinity is higher at high annealing temperatures compared with that at low annealing temperatures, as discussed in Section 3.1; this finding is consistent with previous report findings, whereby reducing the oxygen vacancies degraded the crystallinity of ZGO films [31]. The annealing-temperature dependence of the atomic ratio of Zn to Ga, as determined from the XPS spectra, is shown in Fig. 5g. The Zn/Ga atomic ratio decreases at temperatures above 700 °C owing to the high vapor pressure of zinc. Consequently, oxygen is considered deficient according to a charge-neutral condition owing to the decrease in zinc, and then this oxygen deficiencies improved the crystallinity.

3.3 Optical absorption and E_g of the ZGO nanoparticles and thin films

The UV-Vis spectra of the ZGO nanoparticles and thin films were measured to evaluate the effects of annealing temperature on the optical absorption of the film. The diffuse reflectance spectra of the nanoparticles were measured and converted to the absorption spectrum $F(R_{\infty})$ using the Kubelka–Munk equation [32]. The transmittance spectra of the ZGO thin films were measured and converted into absorption spectra [33]. The $F(R_{\infty})$ and absorbance of the ZGO nanoparticles and thin films are plotted in Fig. 6a. An optical absorption edge is observed at approximately 280 nm in the case of ZGO nanoparticles

and thin films. Tauc plots were obtained for each sample using the absorption spectra; these are plotted in

Fig. 6b [34], where $h\nu$ is the energy of the incident photon.

Fig. 6 (a) Ultraviolet-visible absorption spectra and (b) Tauc plot of the hydrothermally synthesized ZGO

nanoparticles and thin films at different annealing temperatures. The inset in (b) shows schematically how

E_g is determined, whereby the dashed line indicates the extrapolation of the linear part of the Tauc plot. (c)

Relationship between E_g and annealing temperatures of the ZGO thin films. The dashed line represents the

E_g value of the ZGO nanoparticles

E_g was determined by extrapolating the straight part of the curve to the energy axis, as shown in the inset of Fig. 6b; more details are provided in Fig. S1a–e. The obtained E_g values are plotted as a function of the annealing temperature in Fig. 6c. The E_g of the ZGO nanoparticles was 4.63 eV (which is between the corresponding E_g values of the ZGO thin films annealed at 500 and 600 °C). Although the absolute values of E_g are not comparable between the ZGO nanoparticles and thin films because different methods were used to obtain their absorption spectra, the results of the ZGO thin films were compared. Considering the thin films, E_g decreased by approximately 0.11 eV from 4.70 eV at 500 °C to 4.59 eV at 800 °C. The nanoparticles had a radius of approximately 5 nm based on the average particles size of 9.94 nm (Fig. 2c). Owing to aggregation at increasing annealing temperatures, the quantum size effect weakened as the crystallite size increased with respect to the exciton's Bohr radius of 2.72 nm in ZGO (Fig. 4d) [35, 36], resulting in decreased E_g (Fig. 6c) [37]. Nevertheless, the even ZGO thin film annealed at 800 °C still retained the high E_g value of 4.59 eV.

3.4 Photocurrent characteristics of the ZGO thin films for SB irradiation

The applicability of the ZGO thin films prepared using hydrothermally synthesized ZGO nanoparticles as SB photodetectors was considered by evaluating their electrical responses to SB and non-SB UV irradiation. Figure 7a–d show the I – V characteristics of the ZGO thin films. For all ZGO thin films,

the currents increased upon irradiation with SB light at 254 nm, indicating the generation of photocurrent (I_p). Meanwhile, the intensity of the current under non-SB UV irradiation conditions (365 nm) was similar to that of I_D (without irradiation). These results indicate the capability of the present ZGO films to distinguish between SB light and non-SB light.

As shown in Fig. 7f, the repetition of the photocurrent response to SB light irradiation was confirmed for the ZGO thin film annealed at 800 °C, where the photocurrent increased with the applied voltage. However, the rise and decay times of the photocurrent were fluctuated, changing from irradiation to irradiation; in a few cases, the photocurrent saturated during the irradiation period of 60 s. As shown in Fig. 7g, for the tested ZGO thin films, the best rise and decay times were 2.27 s and 1.13 s, respectively. These rise and decay times were approximately an order of magnitude longer than those of the ZGO film fabricated using metal-organic chemical vapor deposition (MOCVD) [38]. This is thought to be due to the high density of charge trap states in the tested ZGO thin films because there were large numbers of oxygen vacancies, grain boundaries, and adsorbed oxygen, that acted as charge trap states compared with the ZGO thin films fabricated by MOCVD [38–40]. For future work, it is necessary to suppress the charge trap states other than oxygen vacancies and to evaluate the responsivity, external quantum efficiency, and detectivity in addition to the rise and decay times in the SB photodetectors fabricated using the present ZGO thin films.

Fig. 7 I - V characteristics of the ZGO thin films annealed at (a) 500 °C, (b) 600 °C, (c) 700 °C, and (d) 800 °C without irradiation (dark condition) and under UV irradiation conditions (254 nm and 365 nm). (e) I_p (red), I_D (black), and I_p/I_D (green) under UV irradiation conditions (254 nm) at an applied voltage of 40 V against the annealing temperatures. (f) Time dependence of current of ZGO thin film annealed at 800 °C for the multicycle SB light irradiation at applied voltages of 5, 10, 20, 30, and 40 V. (g) Time dependence of current of ZGO thin film annealed at 800 °C for single-cycle solar blind irradiation at the biasing voltage of 30 V. The rise time is defined as the time required to achieve a current change from 10 % to 90 % of the maximum current intensity, and the decay time is defined as the time required for a current change from 90 % to 10 % of the maximum current intensity.

Figure 7e shows the plots of I_p , I_D , and I_p/I_D ratio as a function of the annealing temperature under SB light irradiation conditions (at 254 nm) at an applied voltage of 40 V. As the annealing temperature increased, I_D decreased by approximately an order of magnitude, whereas I_p was relatively stable. Consequently, I_p/I_D increased eight-fold from 2.3 at 500 °C to 20.3 at 800 °C. Based on the results in Section 3.2, the decrease in I_D was attributed to the improved crystallinity resulting from the increase in oxygen deficiencies at high annealing temperatures. Thus, these results demonstrate the control of I_p/I_D by the annealing temperature during the ZGO thin-film preparation period for future SB device applications.

Conduction carriers can be generated from elemental defects, such as oxygen vacancies [10, 21, 41]. However, according to the results shown in Figs. 5f and 7e, the increase in oxygen vacancies did not directly increase I_p . Similarly, the increase in oxygen vacancies did not increase I_D ; instead, a decrease in I_D was observed. In polycrystalline thin films, both the internal parts of the grains and the grain boundaries contribute to electrical conduction, which thus depends on the grain size and density [42–45]. Moreover, the quantity and distribution of oxygen vacancies varied in the grain interiors and at the grain boundaries [46]. In the present ZGO thin films, the grain size and number of oxygen vacancies increased with the annealing temperature, as shown in Figs. 4d and 5f. However, the study of the individual effects of these properties on electrical conduction is beyond the scope of this study. These should be clarified in future studies by separately evaluating the electrical conduction of the grain interior and boundaries using impedance measurements, local elemental analysis, and other techniques.

4. Conclusion

Polycrystalline ZGO thin films were fabricated on a quartz substrate using hydrothermally synthesized ZGO nanoparticles with large amounts of oxygen and zinc deficiencies. The substrates coated with ZGO nanoparticles were annealed at different temperatures. Although surface morphology demonstrated minimal variations with the annealing temperature, the crystallite size increased during annealing. The increase in crystallite decreased E_g from 4.70 eV at 500 °C to 4.59 eV at 800 °C by

weakening the quantum size effect, but E_g value still remained high. The ZGO thin films led to the generation of I_P under SB light irradiation conditions (at 254 nm) at an applied voltage of 40 V, while I_P was not generated under UV irradiation (at 365 nm) and dark conditions; that is, the ZGO thin films were able to distinguish between SB light and non-SB light. In addition, the ZGO thin film annealed at 800 °C showed the repetition of photocurrent response to SB light irradiation, where the photocurrent increased with the applied voltage. I_P/I_D increased by a factor of 8.8 as the annealing temperature was increased from 500 °C to 800 °C owing to the decrease of I_D . The decrease in I_D was attributed to the improvement of crystallinity resulting from the increase in oxygen vacancies at high annealing temperatures. Therefore, controlling the annealing temperature can improve the photocurrent characteristics. The proposed ZGO thin films and its preparation technique can be used for durable SB photodetectors. In future studies, the electrical conduction of the grain interior and boundaries will be analyzed separately to determine their roles in the performance of the proposed ZGO thin film.

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Statements and Declarations

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Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interest.

Data availability

The data sets generated during and/or analyzed during the current study are available from corresponding author on reasonable request.

Author contributions

All authors contributed to the study conception and design. Material preparation, XRD measurement, UV-Vis measurement, and photocurrent measurement were performed by Satoshi Ishii, Kazutoshi Fukasaku and Kouhei Aiba. XPS measurement was performed by Reiya Kase. TEM observation was performed by Michiyuki Yoshida. The data analysis was performed by Satoshi Ishii. The first draft of the manuscript was written by Satoshi Ishii. Takayuki Nakane, Yasuharu Ohgoe and Takashi Naka review and edit manuscript, and all authors commented on previous versions of the manuscript. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.